

KEY INDICATORS

With 320,517 hectares, Hungary had 6.4% of its farmland under organic management, which was lower than the EU average of 10.6% but similar to that of the other EU-13 countries. Organic farmland more than quadrupled from 2001-2022; growth was thus similar to that in the European Union. Retail sales data is not available for Hungary.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

79,178 ha (1.7%)

320,517 ha (6.4%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

305%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

121,750 ha (3%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

21,163 ha (13.2%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

177,604 ha (24.2%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

1,740 MT (9.5%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

1,040 (0.1%)

6,189 (2.7%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

4 (2021)

Processors

N/D

468

Importers

N/D

49

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

725 MT

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN HUNGARY

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Nebih, Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Hungarian CAP Strategic Plan targets 5% of land to be supported as organic in 2027, nearly 2.5 times the area supported in 2018. However, the proportion of certified organic land supported in 2018 was relatively low, at 55%, so that the increase in certified area may be lower. An increase of 21% in expenditure per hectare is planned, resulting in a near trebling of expenditure on organic support by 2027. Despite this, the planned share of total CAP and environmental expenditures are relatively low compared with other countries.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	115 kha	279 kha (+142%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	2.2%	5.3% (+142%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	55%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	21 M€	63 M€ (+194%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	186 €	226 € (+21%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	252 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	995 M€	
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,903 M€	8.7%
Total CAP Expenditure	9,977 M€	2.5%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	147	242	516	734	873
	2023	P2	204	458	1097	1762	1132
Change from 2019 to 2023			+39%	+89%	+113%	+140%	+30%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	147	172	516	568	674
	2023	P2	204	349	664	967	1097
Change from 2019 to 2023			+38%	+103%	+29%	+70%	+63%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	+41%	0%	+29%	+29%
	2023		0%	+31%	+65%	+82%	+3%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The current Hungarian OAP is targeting 10% of land to be certified organic in 2027, twice the area planned to be supported as organic in the CAP strategic plan, implying a continuing significant area of organic land not receiving support. The current plan also includes market and procurement targets as well as targets for individual actions, with a strong focus on development of marketing and information initiatives.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2014-21	N/D	N/D
Current Action Plan	2022-27	10% of UAA by 2027	5% of market by 2027 / 20% procurement by 2027

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2014 - 2021)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2022 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Hungary in 2020 was 9.5%. Hungary was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. There is no specific reference to aquaculture in the national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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